

ELLIPSIS IN STYLISTICS

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Annotation: In the article we will study the use of ellipsis, using of ellipsis allows authors to move a story along without getting bogged down in unnecessary details, ellipsis points, The use of ellipsis points in formal writing is different from the stylistic use of ellipsis in literature, The importance of using ellipsis, Disadvantage of Ellipsis.

Key words: ellipsis, stylistics, ellipsis points, an interface phenomenon between syntax, semantics

“Ellipsis” is a Latin word, but it can also be found in Greek as “ellipsis.” These words both mean “to fall short, or leave out.” Ellipsis is a grammatical term and, as such, is used in two main ways. When it is a written symbol that appears as a sequence of dots, usually three (...), they will indicate that parts of a word or sentence have been omitted. These are called ellipsis points.

The use of ellipsis can also be more stylistic. This is when a word or phrase is left out, or omitted, from a sentence. The words omitted may be necessary to make a sentence syntactically correct but they are not necessary for a reader to fully understand the sentence’s meaning.

You can also take this context a step further when you are writing and want to omit larger spans of time. This use of ellipsis allows authors to move a story along without getting bogged down in unnecessary details. This use might be easiest to understand if you think of the concept of “time-lapse”. Ellipsis noun, and it is pronounced (ih-lip-seez). Its plural is ‘ellipses’.

Here are examples of ellipsis points:

1. This is the beginning of Abraham Lincoln’s famous Gettysburg Address. The ellipses points are used to let the reader know that this is only part of the entire quote:

Fourscore and seven years ago our fathers brought forth...the proposition that all men are created equal.

2. Here is a stylistic example of an ellipsis where a word is omitted:

In the baseball game, our team scored four homeruns, the other team, only two...

In this example, the words “homeruns” is left out of the second part of the sentence. The sentence remains complete, however, because the context makes it clear that the author is referring to homeruns, not something else.

3. For an example of ellipsis in the larger time-lapse sense. Think of the Harry Potter series, by J.K. Rowling. This series spans the course of seven years. However, the focus of the plot is on the time that the central character, Harry, spends at his boarding school, Hogwarts. The mundane details of his boring summer vacations are greatly left out.

Describing how these work can become as technical as the study of grammar itself. This is because an ellipsis is always associated with something else in the sentence—the part that is left out. The best scholars describe ellipsis as “an interface phenomenon between syntax, semantics, and information structure.” Simply put, each type of ellipsis corresponds directly to the parts of speech that are being omitted and refers to what sort of ‘hole’ is left behind in the sentence.

The most important thing to understand about them is that, if something is left out of a sentence, but you can still understand the sentence, you have an ellipsis.

In writing, we quote and borrow all the time. When you leave out words or phrases, however, you change meaning. Ellipsis points are important because they tell your readers that something is missing. The points help your audience understand that you have only quoted part of something, and that they can go back and fill in the blank should they wish to. If you have used the ellipsis points responsibly, they should not need to.

Giving your audience this piece of information is particularly important in a field like journalism, where facts and opinions can be twisted easily and quickly. Consider these two sentences:

Correct: Susie’s paper was a strongly written, albeit factually inaccurate and alarmist, account of the downtown protest.

Incorrect: Susie’s paper was a strongly written...account of the downtown protest.

The second sentence is an irresponsible use of ellipsis because it leaves out vital details and fundamentally changes the meaning of the sentence.

The use of ellipsis points in formal writing is different from the stylistic use of ellipsis in literature. The stylistic use of ellipsis in creative writing refers to an even larger application of its grammatical context. Rather than just informing us that some details are missing, it also helps us to hear the character’s voices.

Example: The Great Gatsby, by F. Scott Fitzgerald shows us perfect examples of a time lapse ellipsis (as he reminisces) and gives voice to the character:

His life had been confused and disordered since then, but if he could once return to a certain starting place and go over it all slowly, he could find out what that thing was . . .

Using ellipsis in English riddles.

1. What can you catch, but not throw? Answer: A cold.
2. What begins with T, finishes with T, and has T in it? Answer: A teapot.
3. What goes up, but never comes back down? Answer: Your age.
4. What two things can you never eat for breakfast? Answer: Lunch and dinner.
5. The more you take, the more you leave behind. What am I? Answer: Footprints..
6. What has four legs but can’t walk? Answer: A table.
7. What is full of holes but still holds water? Answer: A sponge.
8. What has an eye but can’t see anything? Answer: A needle.
9. What has a key, but can’t open a locked door? Answer: A monkey.

Disadvantage of Ellipsis: Ellipsis in the wording and choice of words is one of the most serious mistakes that causes mental confusion and even leads to wrong conclusions. Such errors sometimes occur as a result of "correction" by press staff trying to reduce the size of the article, and sometimes due to the author's inattention. For example: Our souls and material manifestations of our souls are inherited from us to the generations. (Newspaper.) There is ambiguity in the word "our soul" in this sentence, and after "and" the words "shu"

have been omitted. However, such a descent was absolutely impossible at this place. Although Abdulla's poem is sometimes not free from oppositions, which are raised as much as possible. but o g o h encourages drinking (Newspaper). Carelessness in choosing words and forming compounds is noticeable in this sentence as well. Another mistake in using words is to use words in a different way. Such a defect occurs in radio and television broadcasts, as well as in the press. Nowadays, when the struggle to improve speech culture has intensified, and people demand accuracy in their statements of opinion, it is not normal to make such mistakes.

The importance of using ellipsis, or omission, stylistically, is that you can cover a lot of ground without getting bogged down in unnecessary details. When you are writing, you cannot include every detail all of the time. Nor would you want to, and nor should you. Whether you are using ellipsis in the larger stylistic sense or using the physical ellipsis points, this literary device helps to reduce clutter and sharpen the focus on the point you are trying to make

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